

CODE of CONDUCT

General intention

The CDRterra community developed this Code of Conduct to communicate our common understanding of basic values and rules for respectful cooperation and communication. These guidelines aim at identifying the core ethical values for conducting research within the CDRterra community, establishing an example and developing this further within the wider climate science community and partner institutions.

The CDRterra Code of Conduct applies to everyone, regardless of their level or field of experience, gender or gender identity, age, national origin or nationality, cultural background, religious creed, sexual orientation, family status or health condition.

We encourage all CDRterra members to implement and transmit the values of the Code of Conduct within and outside the CDRterra environment such as their working groups, research departments and institutes. Please note that this document is not legally binding and no claims can be deducted, but reflects the high ambitions of all consortia within CDRterra to communicate and cooperate in a respectful manner.

Welcoming working conditions

We promote a good work-life-balance. This includes scheduling meetings only during regular working hours, taking holidays, no work obligations during weekends, aside from research cruises or longer-term laboratory experiments, and regular balancing of overtime.

Support is provided for those with family obligations to the best extent possible. Meetings take place at family- friendly times whenever possible.

Principal investigators, supervisors, and scientists in leading positions are role models for practising a good work-life balance and should discuss with their team members ways of improving working conditions.

A CDRterra counsellor is available who can be asked for advice in case of conflicts and problems. All requests are handled confidentially. Further details on the counsellors' role and the request procedure can be found in the CDRterra internal communication document (<https://cdrterra.de/en/about-cdrterra>).

The counsellor as well as the CDRterra governance bodies closely work together with the CDRterra partner institutions to solve issues of all kinds to support all members of the research mission.

Scientific ethics

We are aware of our responsibility with respect to freedom of research and research risks. By implementing the CDRterra Innovative and Responsible Research Guidelines (<https://cdrterra.de/en/about-cdrterra>) we follow ethical principles, not only with respect to the way research is conducted but also with respect to the research output.

Scientific transparency and communication

A core part of research transparency is to make research open. We therefore make our research methods, outputs and data open and available, as far as intellectual property rights or confidentiality obligations are not affected.

We follow important guidelines, for example the fulfilment of regulations regarding (co-) authorship on publications and the FAIR* principle of data availability and accessibility. This is defined in the CDRterra Research Data Policy (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7304407).

We are aware of the social responsibility of our science and participate actively in political and social debates concerning scientific fields in which we operate or to which we can contribute with our expertise.

We inform the public openly and transparently about our research.

*FAIR data = findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable

Value of diversity and individualism

We encourage and acknowledge the importance of diversity in research teams by fostering staff with different backgrounds, ways of living, beliefs and nature to bring in diversified experiences, research ideas, ways to organise work and communicate.

A diverse working environment supports an open exchange of individual ideas and the development of diverse practises to improve the cooperation between scientists and to advance research.

Value of internationalism and interculturalism

We desire and value a highly international and intercultural research community bringing in different perspectives on scientific questions, research methods and experimental set-ups for the improvement of our research.

We will establish international cooperation and exchange with projects that pursue similar goals.

We endeavour to develop and maintain a respectful cooperation by acting and communicating in culturally sensitive ways within and outside the research community.

Zero tolerance

for unjust treatment and harassment

Everyone shall be treated equally and fairly.

Specific individual requirements such as different levels of familiarity with the German science system, different levels of experience, various contract situations and family obligations should be taken into consideration in our dealings with and expectations of each other.

Discrimination, mobbing and sexual harassment are under no circumstances tolerated in all working environments, including fieldwork and research cruises.

Everyone shall be free to speak up about inappropriate and unjust behaviour or make use of the formal (anonymous) channels provided by their respective institutions and the CDRterra Counsellor.

Career development

We actively promote career development at all levels by supporting professional training and personal development.

Early career scientists at the doctoral level are encouraged to enrol in graduate schools and postdocs in existing peer-networks to receive training and structured career support.

Career development support is expected from supervisors, mentors, principal investigators and all other scientists in leading positions.

Environmental responsibility

The aim of CDRterra is to develop methods to mitigate climate change.

We attempt to act as sustainably as possible when conducting our research and while working together. For example, at meetings, catering should be regional and vegetarian and disposable products should be avoided. Printing and other outreach materials and products should be climate and environmentally friendly produced.

The meeting and event venues are chosen so that they are easily accessible by train for all partners. For business trips, the train is generally preferable.

CDRterra

In the CDRterra research program, more than 100 researchers in ten collaborative projects are investigating how and to what extent land-based CO₂ removal methods can contribute to limiting climate change. Political, economic, ecological, technical and societal issues are taken into account. The aim is to comprehensively and uniformly evaluate the potential and side effects of the various methods. This is also done in comparison to marine methods, which are investigated by the research mission CDRmare. On this basis, a societally acceptable, politically feasible and ecologically and economically sensible portfolio of CDR methods can be developed - in dialogue with politics, industry and the public.

Acknowledgement

This Code of Conduct is based on the Code of Conduct of our partner research programme CDRmare (DOI 10.3289/CDRmare.16). We sincerely thank our colleagues for their support.

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